

Synergy of Bronchoscopy and HRCT in Predicting Disease Activity in Sputum Negative Pulmonary Tuberculosis

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background & Methods: The aim of the study was to evaluate the Synergy of Bronchoscopy and HRCT in Predicting Disease Activity in sputum negative Pulmonary Tuberculosis. HRCT scans were assessed for the presence of centri-lobular nodules, tree in bud pattern, larger nodules, masses, lobular consolidations, cavities, bronchoceles, ground glass opacities and mediastinal lymph node enlargement.

Results: The most frequently observed CT findings (in order of decreasing frequency) were consolidation, mediastinal lymphadenopathy, tree-in-bud appearance, and nodules. Tree-in-bud appearance was the only significant finding associated with active PTB status ($P < 0.001$, OR = 5.10 [2.37–10.99, 95% CI]). Of the 21 PTB-confirmed patients, 16 (71.6%) patients were rapidly diagnosed in less than 1 week by bronchial washing AFB smear, CBNAAT and/or biopsy, and 5 patients were confirmed several weeks later by bronchial washing or sputum culture results. The sensitivity of FOB in the rapid diagnosis of active PTB was 75.9% (95% CI, 69.0–78.6%).

Conclusion: HRCT alone was limited for the diagnosis of active PTB, but the combination of FOB and HRCT may improve the sensitivity of FOB in the rapid diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB. Based on our results, we suggest that physicians actively consider performing FOB and HRCT in sputum smear-negative patients suspected of TB.

Keywords: Bronchoscopy, HRCT, sputum, negative & Pulmonary Tuberculosis.

Study Design: Observational Study.

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Introduction

Pulmonary tuberculosis is a widespread problem, especially in our country where it is one of the leading causes of mortality. The global strategy to control TB is prompt diagnosis, notification, and successful treatment of patients with active disease [1]. Sputum microscopy and Chest x-ray often used in PTB screening, but in sputum smear-negative TB patients many show atypical x-ray patterns or normal findings. [2]

Pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) is one of the major health problems worldwide. PTB is known to the mankind since time immemorial. It is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally with an estimated 9 million cases and 1.5 million deaths each year. Every 4 s, an individual contracts tuberculosis and one of them dies every 10 s [3]. The emergence of multidrug TB and increasing

number of immunocompromised population are threats to the global TB control.

However, all patients with PTB will not show AFB in their sputum smears. About 40–60% of patients with suspected active PTB either clinically or radiologically may fail to produce sputum, or when it is available AFB may be negative on repeated smear examinations [4]. Even though mycobacterial cultures are more sensitive than AFB smears (80–85%), culture results usually require 3–8 weeks. Chest x-ray is often used for PTB screening, but many cases with sputum smear-negative TB show atypical x-ray patterns or normal findings [5]. Sputum smear-negative PTB may have mild or no respiratory symptoms and clinical manifestations [6].

High-resolution computed tomography high value in predicting the activity of pulmonary tuberculosis

[7]. As 30% to 50% of the bearers of pulmonary tuberculosis have a negative sputum smear or have no sputum, HRCT and fiberoptic bronchoscopy acquires a special importance HRCT helps in assessing the pattern of involvement of lung parenchyma and predicting disease activity .

Typical CT findings of active pulmonary tuberculosis include centrilobular nodules tree-in-bud appearance, lobular consolidation, cavitation, and bronchial wall thickening. The CT findings of inactive or healed pulmonary tuberculosis include calcified nodules or consolidation, irregular linear opacity and parenchymal bands [8].

Aims and Objective

The aim of this study was to evaluate the diagnostic value of FOB with HRCT in the diagnosis of active PTB in patients suspected of PTB but presenting with a negative sputum smear.

Material and Methods

We retrospectively reviewed the clinical records and FOB and HRCT results of all patients with suspected PTB who visited the pulmonary clinic of BMGMC, Shahdol (M.P.) in last six month from December 2023 to May 2024. The patients were subjected to HRCT thorax.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Age of at least 18 years with clinical or radiographic suspicion of active PTB
2. Negative AFB smear results of 2 or more sputum or failure to expectorate sputum
3. Patient received both FOB and HRCT within 1 month due to suspected PTB before initiation of anti-TB Drug.
4. When FOB was performed, a bronchial washing from the affected lung was acquired for AFB smear, mycobacterial culture and CBNAAT for all patients

Exclusion criteria:

1. AFB smear-positive patients
2. Patients who show clinical and radiological improvement after initiation of anti-tuberculosis medication
3. Patients with mass or neoplastic lesions

Diagnostic Criteria

- HRCT scans were assessed for the presence of centri-lobular nodules, tree in bud pattern, larger nodules, masses, lobular consolidations, cavities, bronchoceles, ground glass opacities and mediastinal lymph node enlargement.
- A rapid diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB by a methods that provide results within 1 week:
 - Positive AFB smear.
 - Positive CBNAAT.
 - Caseating granuloma upon biopsy.

Analysis

Data were analyzed with SPSS software. All tests of significance were two-sided and a P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. Odds ratios (ORs) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CIs) were calculated. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV) for the diagnosis of active PTB disease were calculated for each diagnostic test.

Result

- Active PTB was diagnosed in 21 patients (42.9%), of which 18 (85.7%) had positive TB cultures and 3 (14.3%) cases were confirmed by pathology and CBNAAT
- Non-TB diagnoses were made in 29 patients
- Chest x-rays showed a higher positive rate in the TB group than in the non-TB group (52.3% vs. 20.7%, respectively, P < 0.001).

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of all sputum smear-negative TB suspects

Characteristic	All suspects N = 50	TB N = 21	Non-TB N= 29	P-value
Age, years (Mean ± SD)	51.0 ± 18.2	45.3 ± 18.8	55.4 ± 16.6	0.002
Male, n (%)	27/50	10/21	17/29	0.256
Previous TB history, n (%)	13/50	3/21	10/29	0.014
CXR positivity, n (%)	17/50	11/21	6/29	<0.001
Active pulmonary TB, n (%)	21/50	21/21		
Cultured confirmed, n (%)		18/21		
Biopsy confirmed, n (%)		3/21		

Clinical characteristics and HRCT findings in sputum smear-negative TB suspects

Table 2: First presenting symptoms of patients with sputum smear-negative TB

Symptoms	All suspects N = 50	TB N = 21	Non-TB N = 29	P-value	OR (95% CI)
Cough, n (%)	28/50	13/21	15/29	0.147	1.70 (0.827-3.493)
Sputum, n (%)	17/50	07/21	10/29	1.000	1.00 (0.473-2.114)
Fever, n (%)	11/50	5/21	6/29	0.531	1.31 (0.559-3.087)
Hemoptysis, n (%)	12/50	3/21	9/29	0.009	0.30 (0.117-0.757)

- Only hemoptysis (P = 0.009, OR = 0.30 [0.12–0.76, 95% CI]) was negatively correlated with active PTB in sputum smear-negative suspects
- HRCT findings in the diagnosis of PTB showed a significant difference between TB and non-TB patients (P < 0.001)
- The most frequently observed CT findings (in order of decreasing frequency) were consolidation, mediastinal lymphadenopathy, tree-in-bud appearance, and nodules. Tree-in-bud appearance was the only significant finding associated with active PTB status (P < 0.001, OR = 5.10 [2.37–10.99, 95% CI]) (Table3)

Table 3: Multivariate regression analysis of CT findings in sputum smear-negative TB suspects

Characteristic	All suspects N = 50	TB N = 21	Non-TB N = 29	P-value	OR (95% CI)
Consolidation, n (%)	35/50	15/21	20/29	0.726	1.05 (0.484-2.257)
Nodule, n (%)	20/50	9/21	11/29	0.435	1.24 (0.602-2.541)
Cavity, n (%)	9/50	6/21	3/29	0.050	3.08 (1.195-7.924)
Tree-in-bud, n (%)	21/50	13/21	8/29	<0.001	5.10 (2.366-10.991)
Mediastinal LAP, n (%)	21/50	10/21	11/29	0.940	1.55 (0.756-3.167)

CONSOLIDATION

TREE IN BUD

CENTRILOBULAR NODUE

CAVITARY LESIONS

CHEST XRAY, HRCT AND BRONCHOSCOPY OF SAME PT

Table 4: Bronchoscopic findings in 21 patients confirmed to have active PTB

	TB	Culture confirmed	Biopsy confirmed
	N = 21	N = 18	N = 3
Bronchial washing culture	16/21	16/18	0/3
Bronchial washing AFB smear	5/21	4/18	0/3
Bronchial washing CBNAAT	13/21	12/18	0/3
Bronchoscopic biopsy (TBB + bronchial biopsy)	20/21	17/18	3/3
Bronchial washing AFB smear + CBNAAT + bronchoscopic biopsy	16/21	13/18	3/3

Of the 21 PTB-confirmed patients, 16 (71.6%) patients were rapidly diagnosed in less than 1 week by bronchial washing AFB smear, CBNAAT and/or biopsy, and 5 patients were confirmed several weeks later by bronchial washing or sputum culture results.

Diagnostic accuracy of FOB and HRCT in sputum smear-negative TB suspects

- The diagnostic accuracy of FOB, HRCT, and the combination of FOB and HRCT in sputum smear-negative TB suspects is summarized in Table 5. The sensitivity of FOB in the rapid diagnosis of active PTB was 75.9% (95% CI, 69.0–78.6%)
- The specificity was 97.2% (95% CI, 92.0–99.2%).
- The sensitivity of HRCT in the diagnosis of active PTB was 85.2% (95% CI, 75.2–92.3%), and the specificity was 72.2% (95% CI, 64.7–77.6%).
- The PPV of FOB was 95.3% (95% CI, 86.7–98.7%) and the NPV of FOB was 84.3% (95% CI, 79.8–86.1%) in the rapid diagnosis of active PTB. These values were higher than the PPV of HRCT (69.7% [95% CI, 61.5–75.5%]) and similar to the NPV of HRCT (86.7% [95% CI, 77.7–93.1%]).
- The combination of FOB and HRCT improved the sensitivity to 96.3% and the NPV to 96.2%.

Discussion

The sputum smear microscopy for AFB for the diagnosis of PTB is cost effective and highly specific. However, all patients with pulmonary tuberculosis will not reveal AFB in the sputum. Also, there are other factors, such as lack of sputum production, low bacterial yield, and improper or incorrect sampling. A smear-negative culture-positive state has been observed in 22–61% of cases [9]. Mycobacterial culture takes 3–8 weeks for the diagnosis of PTB, which delays the treatment [10]. Serological immune markers are also not reliable indicators for the diagnosis of PTB. Early diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary

tuberculosis is the vital step in preventing the disease mortality and the morbidity. Patients with smear-negative PTB can act as a means of transmitting the disease in the community and preclude the early diagnosis and the treatment, often leading to irreversible lung complications in the infected individuals [11]. If these patients were left untreated, 64% of them would require chemotherapy within 12 months [12]. This subset poses a real challenge to the pulmonologists [13]: delayed diagnosis can lead to spread of the disease or irreversible pulmonary complications and the empirical treatment can result in unwanted therapy with its side effects or the emergence of multidrug-resistant strains.

In this retrospective study, we found that FOB showed high sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV in the rapid diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB, and the combination of FOB and HRCT increased the sensitivity and NPV.

Several previous studies evaluated clinical characteristics and scoring systems for the diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB. We find that tree-in-bud appearance was a meaningful HRCT finding in the diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB. Recently, several studies have reported that tree-in-bud appearance, lobular consolidation and large nodules were positively associated with active PTB in sputum smear-negative TB suspects [14].

In previous studies, FOB had a sensitivity of 80–93% and a specificity of 70–95% [15] for rapid diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB, and HRCT had a sensitivity of 60–80% and a specificity of 50–70% [16]. FOB is also useful for the exclusion of non-TB cases from patients suspected of having active PTB with a high specificity and NPV in our setting. The combination of FOB with HRCT increased the sensitivity to 96.3% and NPV to 96.2%.

Conclusion

HRCT alone was limited for the diagnosis of active PTB, but the combination of FOB and HRCT may improve the sensitivity of FOB in the rapid diagnosis of sputum smear-negative PTB. Based on our results, we suggest that physicians actively

consider performing FOB and HRCT in sputum smear-negative patients suspected of TB.

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